

Phylogeny and disparate selection signatures suggest two genetically independent domestication events of pea (*Pisum* L.)

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Supplementary material

Figure S1: LD decay over physical distance in *P.s. ssp. sativum* and *P. abyssinicum*. Dotted lines represent the half decay.

Figure S2: Distribution of SNP density over linkage groups. Outer circle (green): filtered variant set. Inner circle (red): LD pruned variant set.

E

	Missing genotype calls (%)		Observed heterozygosity (H_{obs})		Minor allele frequency		Sites' nucleotide diversity (π)	
	Filtered	LD pruned	Filtered	LD pruned	Filtered	LD pruned	Filtered	LD pruned
Minimum	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0100	0.0100	0.0198	0.0198
1st Quartile	0.0324	0.0324	0.0000	0.0000	0.0188	0.0175	0.0369	0.0345
Median	0.1134	0.1113	0.0031	0.0041	0.0422	0.0361	0.0810	0.0697
Mean	0.1404	0.1401	0.0098	0.0099	0.0944	0.0820	0.1442	0.1288
3rd Quartile	0.2348	0.2348	0.0092	0.0101	0.1151	0.0973	0.2040	0.1759
Maximum	0.3988	0.3988	0.9669	0.9669	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000	0.5000

Figure S3: Violin plots of distribution of missing genotype calls (A), observed heterozygosity (B), minor allele frequency (C) and sites' nucleotide diversity (π ; D) of the entire SNP set and the LD pruned SNP set. Table of summary statistics corresponds to these distributions (E).

Figure S4: Map depicting sample locations of wild *P. sativum* samples which are genetically closest to *P.s.* ssp. *sativum*. The closest clade is marked in green, the second closest one in red.

A

Figure S5: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC3. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S6: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC4. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S7: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC5. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S8: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC6. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S9: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC7. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S10: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC8. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S11: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC9. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S12: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC10. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

- P.s. ssp. sativum*
- P. abyssinicum*
- ELA1
- ELA2
- ELA3
- ELA4
- ELA2
- ELA3

B

Figure S13: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC11. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S14: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC12. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S15: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC13. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S16: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC14. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S17: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC15. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

- P. ssp. sativum*
- ELA2
- ELA2
- P. abyssinicum*
- ELA3
- ELA1
- ELA4
- ELA3

Figure S18: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC16. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S19: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC17. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S20: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC18. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S21: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC19. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S22: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC20. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S23: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC21. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S24: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC22. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S25: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC23. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S26: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC24. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S27: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC25. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S28: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC26. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S29: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC27. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S31: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding SC29. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

A

Figure S33: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding AC2. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.

Figure S34: Neighbor-joining tree (only bootstrap values above 80%; A) and haplotype patterns (B) of the 6Mbp window surrounding AC3. Red shaded area marks of the gene where candidate SNPs are located in.